

Trends in spectral parameters and nephelauxetic ratio values for some lanthanoid(III)-tiron complexes. Part-II

R. Singhai*, V. K. Tiwari and S. N. Limaye

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, India

E-mail : rashmitiwari@epatra.com

Manuscript received 2 September 2002, accepted 21 January 2003

Electronic spectral studies of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Er^{III} in complexation with tiron have been undertaken with a view to evaluate the oscillator strengths (f_{JO}), Judd-Ofelt parameters (τ_λ), inter-electronic repulsion Racah parameters (δE^k) and nephelauxetic ratios ($\delta E^3/\delta E^1$). The parameters have been evaluated in the pH range 4.0–6.0 in order to study the dependence of oscillator strength on pH values. The extent of covalency (via parameter τ_2) and symmetry (via parameters τ_4 and τ_6) in metal-ligand interaction have been estimated with the help of τ_λ parameters. The metal-ligand bonding pattern has been studied in the light of changes in Racah parameters and the nephelauxetic ratio. The oscillator strength values for some specific hypersensitive transitions were found to be significantly large.

In continuation with our earlier studies on the electronic spectra of lanthanum(III) metal ions in different environments¹, the present work was undertaken with a view to study the trends in spectral parameters and nephelauxetic ratio values for Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Er^{III} in complexation with tiron.

Results and discussion

The data in Table 1 show that the oscillator strength values (f_{JO}) attain a maximum at pH ~5.5, which is the pH of maximum complexation. A pH profile of the oscillator strength values (figure omitted for simplicity) exhibited a maximum at pH 5.5–6.0. Deviations beyond pH 6.5–7.0 may be on account of formation of hydroxo complexes. Table

2 records the f_{JO} values for [Pr^{III}/Nd^{III}/Er^{III}-tiron] at pH 5.5 in the range of maximum complexation. Separate studies on determination of concentration of [Ln(III)-tiron] species at different pH values using SCOGS-NR computer software² show (figure omitted for brevity) good agreement with the above observations. The [Ln(III)-tiron] concentrations were determined using the $\log K_n^{II}$ values for tiron, the pK_w for water and the appropriate $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{ML(OH)}^M$ values for the corresponding binary [ML] and hydroxo-complexes [MLOH]. An increase in the degree of complexation may also be visualized by the variations in the ${}^2P_{1/2}$ assignments for Nd^{III}. The ${}^2P_{1/2}$ assignment sensitive to the M-L interactions and the Ln(III)-donor atom bond³ distance show a decrease in the energy [viz. pH 2.04 E (cm⁻¹) 23532; pH 4.0 E (cm⁻¹) 23491; pH 5.0 E (cm⁻¹) 23407; pH 5.5 E (cm⁻¹) 23387; and pH 6.0 E (cm⁻¹) 23463] with increased pH values, indicating greater release of interelectronic repulsion with increased degree of complexation.

The oscillator strength values (f_{JO}) composed of τ_λ parameters representing Ln(III)-L interactions (τ_2) and the symmetry around Ln(III) metal ion (τ_4 , τ_6) are recorded in Table 3. The parameters exhibit a general sequence, $\tau_2 < \tau_4 < \tau_6$, based on their responses towards the Ln(III)-L interactions. The τ_λ parameters are also found to be higher for Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} than for Er^{III} which may be expected on account of higher symmetry produced with the former two due to their larger Ln(III) ion sizes. The τ_2 parameters are, however, smaller than for identical Nd^{III} showing a lesser

Table 1. Representative f_{JO} values for [Pr^{III}-tiron] complexes at different pHs

pH	$f_{JO} (\times 10^4)$ for			
	1D_2	3P_0	${}^3P_1, {}^1I_6$	3P_2
	16850	20800	21400–21700	22600
	E (cm ⁻¹)	E (cm ⁻¹)	E (cm ⁻¹)	E (cm ⁻¹)
2.00	2.910	2.153	3.012	10.065
(Std)	(3.171)	(2.341)	(4.910)	(12.861)
4.00	3.638	2.217	4.327	18.888
5.00	3.285	2.005	5.095	18.668
5.50	3.491	1.458	5.451	18.154
6.00	3.108	1.640	5.221	15.973

Table 2. Oscillator strength values for some specific prominent electronic transitions of f_{JO} values ($\times 10^4$) [Ln(III)-tiron] complexes at pH ≈ 5.5

Assignment	[Pr ^{III} -tiron]							
	¹ D ₂	³ P ₀	³ P ₁ ; ¹ I ₆	³ P ₂				
E (cm ⁻¹)	16850	20800	21400–21700	22600				
f _{JO}	3.491	1.458	5.451	18.154				
Assignment	[Nd ^{III} -tiron]							
	¹ F _{3/2}	⁴ F _{5/2} ; ² H _{9/2}	⁴ F _{7/2}	⁴ G _{5/2}	³ K _{3/2}	⁴ D _{3/2}		
E (cm ⁻¹)	11450	12500;12600	13500	17300	19000	28300		
f _{JO}	2.383	13.434	11.923	21.923	12.402			
Assignment	[Er ^{III} -tiron]							
	⁴ F _{9/2}	⁴ S _{3/2}	² H _{11/2}	⁴ F _{7/2}	⁴ F _{5/2}	³ G _{9/2}	⁴ G _{11/2}	⁴ G _{9/2}
E (cm ⁻¹)	15300	18400	19200	20500	22200	24600	26400	27400
f _{JO}	9.181	1.022	12.900	9.880	7.318	3.147	13.112	8.907

involvement of covalency for post Gd metal ions than for pre-Gd metal ions. These observations may be ascertained with the changes in IERP-Racah (δE^k) parameters and the nephelauxetic ratio ($\delta E^3/\delta E^1$) values (Table 3). Smaller values of $\delta E^3/\delta E^1$ for Er^{III} than for Nd^{III} indicate a predominantly ionic pattern of bonding.

Table 3. Values of τ_λ parameters δE^3 , δE^1 and $\delta E^3/\delta E^1$ for [Ln(III)-tiron] complexes at pH ≈ 5.5

Parameter	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Er ^{III}
τ_2	-30.84	2.14	-11.84
τ_4	5.05	16.40	7.85
τ_6	51.59	18.82	13.29
δE^1	-231.03	158.39	-14.20
δE^3	3.00	-2.21	4.71
$\delta E^3/\delta E^1$	-0.0130	-0.0140	-0.3313

The studies reveal that the oscillator values are susceptible towards the Ln(III) environment and their degree of complexation. The trends in τ_2 (smaller than τ_4 and τ_6) and $\delta E^3/\delta E^1$ (negative and smaller) values indicate that the Ln(III)-L interactions in the present case are predominantly ionic.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Ln(III) nitrates (99.99% purity; Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) and tiron (Merck, G.R.) were prepared in double-distilled water. HNO₃ (0.1 mol dm⁻³) was used as a reference acid. Carbonate-free NaOH solution (0.2 mol dm⁻³) was used to adjust the pH, which was recorded on an Orion-940 extended ion analyser system. Measured quantities of alkali were added to adjust the pH values; variations in concentrations due to addition of alkali was calculated and used in the calculation for the oscillator

strength values. The solutions of Ln(III) metal ions blank (0.025 mol dm⁻³) and [Ln(III)-tiron] complexes (in 1 : 2 ratio) with total Ln(III) concentration of ≈ 0.025 mol dm⁻³ were prepared and their electronic spectra recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 3B spectrophotometer.

The values of the oscillator strength and Judd-Ofelt parameter were evaluated using Judd-Ofelt⁴ approach. The variations in the inter-electronic repulsion Racah parameters (IERP-Racah) for Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Er^{III} were evaluated using Wong's equations⁵. Pascal compiled self-devised computer software were used to evaluate these spectral parameters using standard equations⁶.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar, for facilities. One of the authors (R.S.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. R. Singhai, S. N. Limaye and M. C. Saxena, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1995, **107**, 523; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 633; *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1997, **53**, 353.
2. D. D. Perrin and I. G. Sayce, *Talanta*, 1967, **14**, 834.
3. K. B. Yatsimirskii and N. K. Devidenko, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1979, **27**, 223.
4. B. R. Judd, *Phys. Rev.*, 1962, **127**, 750; G. S. Ofelt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **37**, 511.
5. E. Y. Wong, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 544.
6. W. T. Carnall, P. R. Fields and B. G. Wybourn, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **42**, 3797; K. Bukietynska and G. R. Choppin, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1970, **50**, 2875; G. R. Choppin and R. L. Fellows, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1974, **3**, 209; R. D. Peacock, *Struct. Bonding*, 1975, **22**, 83.